

Here you can find the supplementary materials, scripts and both generated and used data from the following study:

Natalia Llopis Monferrer, Sarah Romac, Manon Laget, Yasuhide Nakamura, Tristan Biard, Miguel M. Sandin (2025) **Is the gelatinous matrix of *Nassellaria* (*Radiolaria*) a strategy for coping with oligotrophy?** *Environ. Microbiol.* 27 (5), e70098. doi: [10.1111/1462-2920.70098](https://doi.org/10.1111/1462-2920.70098)

This repository is organized in three folders containing:

data:

llops_18S.fasta:	18S rDNA sequences used for phylogenetic analyses
llops_28S.fasta:	28S rDNA sequences used for phylogenetic analyses
longReads_18S.fasta:	18S rDNA sequences associated to Phlebarachnium extracted from 10.6084/m9.figshare.15164772.v3
longReads_28S.fasta:	28S rDNA sequences associated to Phlebarachnium extracted from 10.6084/m9.figshare.15164772.v3
phlebarachnium_28S.fasta:	28S rDNA sequences of Phlebarachnium generated in this study
Scrippsiella_18S.fasta:	18S rDNA sequences of Scrippsiella symbionts generated in this study
states_strict_all.tsv:	Gelatinous matrix states for all sequences used in this study
V4.fasta:	V4 hypervariable region of the 18S rDNA associated to Phlebarachnium extracted from 10.5281/zenodo.7804946

materials: This directory contains all supplementary figures and tables

- figS1_LM.pdf
- figS2_ancestral_BI.pdf
- figS3_symbionts.pdf
- figS4_cooccurrence_networks_sizeFractions.pdf
- figS5_cooccurrence_networks_unknown.pdf
- SupTableS1_NLL_GelatinousMatrix.xlsx
- SupTableS2_NLL_GelatinousMatrix.tsv

scripts: This directory contains the scripts used in this study, organized by figure names.

- fig_3.0_mrBayes.nex
- fig_3.1.sh
- fig_4.0_llops_align_trim05_MC10.xml
- fig_4.1.sh
- fig_4.2_ancestral.xml
- fig_4.3_ancestral.R
- fig_5.0.sh
- fig_5.1.R
- fig_6.0.R
- fig_6.1.jl
- fig_6.2.sh
- fig_6.3.R
- fig_S2_ancestral.R